

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

UDC 517.951.2 .

THE DARBOUX PROBLEM FOR THE NONHOMOGENEOUS GENERALIZED EULER-POISSON-DARBOUX EQUATION

Ismoilov A.

Fergana State University, Fergana

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7032233>

Abstract

In the article a Darboux problem is considered for a generalized nonhomogeneous Euler-Poisson-Darboux equation in the characteristic triangle. A solution of the problem was found using Riemann method. It was proved that the function defined by the found formula actually satisfies the equation and boundary conditions.

Keywords: Darboux problem , nonhomogeneous generalized Euler-Poisson-Darboux equation, Riemann method, Riemann -Hadamard function.

Introduction

Many differential equations of hyperbolic type with two lines of degeneracy in characteristic coordinates reduce to an equation of the form

$$L(u) \equiv u_{\xi\eta} + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta + \xi} + \frac{\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) u_{\xi} + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta + \xi} - \frac{\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) u_{\eta} + \gamma u = f(\xi, \eta). \quad (1)$$

Here, α, β, γ are given real numbers.

In works [1-4] for equation (1) in case $f(\xi, \eta) = 0$ with $\alpha = \gamma = 0$ in the characteristic triangle $\Delta = \{(\xi, \eta) : 0 \leq \xi < \eta \leq 1\}$ nonlocal boundary value problems have been investigated . The solution of the Cauchy problem for the equation $L(u) \equiv 0$ for $\alpha \geq 0, \beta \in [0, 1/2)$ was found by the Riemann method in [5], and in [6] it was found using the Erdelyi-Kober operator. In [7-8] for the equation $L(u) \equiv 0$ in case $0 < \alpha, \beta < 1/2$, the Darboux and Cauchy-Goursat problems were studied. The solutions of these problems have been constructed explicitly by the Riemann method.

Formulation of the problem

Consider the equation (1) in the characteristic triangle Δ of the plane $\xi O \eta$ bounded by segments $\overline{OA} = \{(\xi, \eta) : \eta = \xi, 0 \leq \xi \leq 1\}$, $\overline{CA} = \{(\xi, 1) : 0 \leq \xi \leq 1\}$, $\overline{OC} = \{(0, \eta) : 0 \leq \eta \leq 1\}$, where $0 < \alpha, \beta < 1/2$, and $f(\xi, \eta)$ is a given function.

Darboux's problem. Find a solution $u(\xi, \eta) \in C(\overline{\Delta})$ to the equation (1) satisfying the conditions

$$u(\xi, \xi) = \tau(\xi), \quad 0, \xi, 1, \quad (2)$$

$$u(0, \eta) = \psi(\eta), \quad 0, \eta, 1, \quad (3)$$

where $\tau(\xi)$ and $\psi(\xi)$ are given continuous functions, such that $\psi(0) = \tau(0)$.

The Riemann-Hadamard function of the equation $L(u) = 0$ for conditions (2) and (3) was constructed in [7]:

$$V(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0, \gamma) = \begin{cases} R_1(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0, \gamma), & \text{npu } \eta_0 > \xi, \\ R_4(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0, \gamma), & \text{npu } \eta_0 < \xi, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$R_1(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0, \gamma) = \sigma_0 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} F_3(\beta, \alpha, 1 - \beta, 1 - \alpha; 1 + k; \sigma_2, \sigma_1), \quad (5)$$

$$R_4(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0, \gamma) = \chi \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta}}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-1} \times \\ \times \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{k! (\beta)_k} H_2 \left(1 - \beta - k, 1 - \beta, \alpha, 1 - \alpha; 2 - 2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}, -\sigma_1 \right). \quad (6)$$

where $\chi = \Gamma(1 - \beta) / \Gamma(\beta) \Gamma(2 - 2\beta)$,
 $\sigma_1 = (\xi - \xi_0)(\eta - \eta_0) / (\eta + \xi)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)$.

$\sigma_0 = [(\eta + \xi) / (\eta_0 + \xi_0)]^\alpha [(\eta - \xi) / (\eta_0 - \xi_0)]^\beta$.
 $\sigma_2 = (\xi - \xi_0)(\eta - \eta_0) / (\eta - \xi)(\eta_0 - \xi_0)$.

$\sigma_3 = -\gamma(\xi - \xi_0)(\eta - \eta_0)$, $(\beta)_k = \beta(\beta + 1)\dots(\beta + k - 1) = \Gamma(\beta + k) / \Gamma(\beta)$ is the symbol of Pochhammer, $\Gamma(z)$ is the Euler gamma function, H_2 and F_3 are, respectively, the two variables hypergeometric functions of Horn and Appel [9].

Derivation of the main formula

Function $V(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma)$ has the following properties:

1⁰) it ξ_0, η_0 satisfies equation (1) at $f(\xi, \eta) = 0$, and the adjoint equation in terms of variables ξ, η :

$$L^*(u) \equiv u_{\xi\eta} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \left[\left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta + \xi} + \frac{\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) u \right] - \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \left[\left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta + \xi} - \frac{\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) u \right] + \gamma u = 0;$$

2⁰) $V_\xi - \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta + \xi} - \frac{\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) V = 0$ at $\eta = \eta_0$,

3⁰) $V_\eta - \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta + \xi} + \frac{\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) V = 0$ at $\xi = \xi_0$;

4⁰) $V(\xi_0, \eta_0; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) = 1$;

5⁰) $\lim_{\eta - \xi \rightarrow 0} V(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) = 0$;

6⁰) $\lim_{\eta - \xi \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \left[V_\xi - \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta + \xi} - \frac{\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) V \right]_{\eta = \xi_0 + \varepsilon} - \left[V_\xi - \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta + \xi} - \frac{\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) V \right]_{\eta = \xi_0 - \varepsilon} \right\} = 0, \varepsilon > 0$.

Let be $u(\xi, \eta)$ a solution to the Darboux problem, and $P(\xi_0, \eta_0)$ be an arbitrary point of the domain $\Delta \cup CA$. Let's find $u(\xi_0, \eta_0)$. In a triangle $O'AD'$ bounded by l segments $O'A', AD', O'D'$ lines, , , respectively $\eta = \xi + \varepsilon, \eta = \xi_0 - \varepsilon$ and $\xi = 0$ in a rectangle $D''A''C''C'$ bounded by segments $D''A'', C''C', D''C', A''C''$ of straight lines $\eta = \xi_0 + \varepsilon, \eta = \eta_0, \xi = 0, \xi = \xi_0 - 2\varepsilon$, respectively, the identity

$$VL(u) - uL^*(V) = M_\xi + N_\eta - Vf(\xi, \eta) \equiv 0, \tag{7}$$

where $M = Vu_\eta - uV_\eta + \left(\frac{2\alpha}{\eta + \xi} + \frac{2\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) uV, N = Vu_\xi + uV_\xi - \left(\frac{2\alpha}{\eta + \xi} - \frac{2\beta}{\eta - \xi} \right) uV$.

We integrate identity (7) over the triangle $O'AD'$ and quadrilateral $D''A''C''C'$. Then, passing to the limit at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ and using the properties 1⁰ - 6⁰ of function $V(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma)$ and the boundary conditions (2), (3), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} u(\xi_0, \eta_0) &= \int_0^{\eta_0} \left[\psi'(\eta) + \frac{\alpha + \beta}{\eta} \psi(\eta) \right] V(0, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta + \\ &+ (1 + 2\beta) \chi(\eta_0 - \xi_0)^{1-2\beta} \int_0^{\xi_0} \left(\frac{2\xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{\tau(\xi)}{[(\xi - \xi_0)(\xi - \eta_0)]^{1-\beta}} \times \\ &\times \Xi_2(\alpha, 1 - \alpha, \beta; \sigma_1, \sigma_3) \Big|_{\xi = \eta} d\xi + \int_0^{\xi_0} \int_\xi^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) V(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0) d\eta, \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where $\Xi_2(\alpha, 1 - \alpha, \beta; \sigma_1, \sigma_2) = \sum_{m,n=0}^\infty \frac{(\alpha)_m (1 - \alpha)_m}{(\beta)_{m+n}} \sigma_1^m \sigma_2^n$ is the Humbert function [9].

From the process of obtaining formula (8) it is clear that if there is a solution to the problem $\{(1), (2), (3)\}$, then this solution has the form (8). From (8) at $0 < \alpha, \beta < 1/2, f(\xi, \eta) = 0$ follows the formula obtained in [7].

Let us study formula (8). The first and second terms were studied in [7]. Here we consider the third term. Let us introduce the following notation:

$$F(\xi_0, \eta_0) = \int_0^{\xi_0} d\xi \int_\xi^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) V(\xi_0, \eta_0; \xi, \eta; \gamma) d\eta. \tag{9}$$

Theorem. If the function $f(\xi, \eta)$ can be represented as

$$f(\xi, \eta) = (\eta - \xi)^{\delta - 1} f_1(\xi, \eta), \delta > 0, f_1(\xi, \eta) \in C(\bar{\Delta}), \tag{10}$$

then the function $F(\xi_0, \eta_0)$ in the domain Δ satisfies equation (1) and the boundary conditions

$$\lim_{\eta_0 \rightarrow \xi_0} F(\xi_0, \eta_0) = 0, \quad 0 \leq \xi_0 \leq 1; \quad F(\xi_0, \eta_0)|_{\xi_0=0} = 0, \quad 0 \leq \eta_0 \leq 1. \quad (11)$$

Proof. Taking equality (4) into account, we write (9) as

$$F(\xi_0, \eta_0) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} [F_{1\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0) + F_{4\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)], \quad (12)$$

where

$$F_{1\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0) = \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi_0+\varepsilon}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) R_1(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta, \quad (13)$$

$$F_{4\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0) = \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi+\varepsilon}^{\xi_0-\varepsilon} f(\xi, \eta) R_4(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta. \quad (14)$$

Now, using equalities (13) and (14), we find the derivatives of the function $F_{1\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)$ and $F_{4\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F_{1\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)}{\partial \xi_0} &= \int_{\xi_0+\varepsilon}^{\eta_0} f(\xi_0 - 2\varepsilon, \eta) R_1(\xi_0 - 2\varepsilon, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta - \\ &\quad - \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} f(\xi, \xi_0 + \varepsilon) R_1(\xi, \xi_0 + \varepsilon; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\xi + \\ &\quad + \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi_0+\varepsilon}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_1(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0) d\eta. \\ \frac{\partial F_{1\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)}{\partial \eta_0} &= \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} f(\xi, \eta_0) R_1(\xi, \eta_0; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\xi + \\ &\quad + \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi_0+\varepsilon}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta. \\ \frac{\partial^2 F_{1\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)}{\partial \xi_0 \partial \eta_0} &= f(\xi_0 - 2\varepsilon, \eta_0) R_1(\xi_0 - 2\varepsilon, \eta_0; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) + \\ &\quad + \int_{\xi_0+\varepsilon}^{\eta_0} f(\xi_0 - 2\varepsilon, \eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1(\xi_0 - 2\varepsilon, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta - \\ &\quad - \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} f(\xi, \xi_0 + \varepsilon) \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1(\xi, \xi_0 + \varepsilon; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\xi + \\ &\quad + \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} f(\xi, \eta_0) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_1(\xi, \eta_0; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\xi + \\ &\quad + \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi_0+\varepsilon}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi_0 \partial \eta_0} R_1(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta. \\ \frac{\partial F_{4\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)}{\partial \xi_0} &= \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} f(\xi, \xi_0 - \varepsilon) R_4(\xi, \xi_0 - \varepsilon; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\xi + \\ &\quad + \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi+\varepsilon}^{\xi_0-\varepsilon} f(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_4(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta. \\ \frac{\partial F_{4\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)}{\partial \eta_0} &= \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi+\varepsilon}^{\xi_0-\varepsilon} f(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_4(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta. \\ \frac{\partial^2 F_{4\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)}{\partial \xi_0 \partial \eta_0} &= \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} f(\xi, \xi_0 - \varepsilon) \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_4(\xi, \xi_0 - \varepsilon; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\xi + \\ &\quad + \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi+\varepsilon}^{\xi_0-\varepsilon} f(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi_0 \partial \eta_0} R_4(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta. \end{aligned}$$

Let's make an expression $L[F_{1\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0) + F_{4\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)]$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & L[F_{1\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0) + F_{4\varepsilon}(\xi_0, \eta_0)] = \\
 & = \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi_0+\varepsilon}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi_0 \partial \eta_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_1 + \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} - \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1 + \gamma R_1 \right] d\eta + \\
 & = \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\xi \int_{\xi_0+\varepsilon}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi_0 \partial \eta_0} R_4 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_4 + \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} - \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_4 + \gamma R_4 \right] d\eta + \\
 & \quad + \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} f(\xi, \eta) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} - \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 \right]_{\eta=\eta_0} d\xi + \\
 & \quad + \int_{\xi_0+\varepsilon}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 \right]_{\xi=\xi_0-2\varepsilon} d\eta + \\
 & \quad + \int_0^{\xi_0-2\varepsilon} \left\{ f(\xi, \eta) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_4 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_4 \right]_{\eta=\xi_0-\varepsilon} - \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - f(\xi, \eta) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 \right]_{\eta=\xi_0+\varepsilon} \right\} + \\
 & \quad + f(\xi_0 - 2\varepsilon, \eta_0) R_1(\xi_0 - 2\varepsilon, \eta_0; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma). \tag{15}
 \end{aligned}$$

Due to the properties of the functions R_1 and R_4 , the integrands in the first two iterated integrals are equal to zero.

By expression [9]

$$F_3(\alpha, \alpha', \beta, \beta'; x, y) = \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha')_n (\beta')_n}{(\gamma)_n n!} y^n F(\alpha, \beta, \gamma + n; x),$$

from the equality (5), we obtain

$$R_1(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) = \sigma_0 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n n!} \sigma_1^n F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2). \tag{16}$$

It is easy to verify that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_1 = -\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} R_1 + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} R_1 + \\
 & + \sigma_0 (\sigma_3)'_{\xi_0} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^{k-1}}{k!(k-1)!} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n n!} \sigma_1^n F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) + \\
 & + \sigma_0 (\sigma_1)'_{\xi_0} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n (n-1)!} \sigma_1^n F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) + \\
 & + \sigma_0 (\sigma_2)'_{\xi_0} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n n!} \sigma_1^n \frac{\beta(1-\beta)}{1+k+n} F(1+\beta, 2-\beta, 2+k+n; \sigma_2), \\
 & \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1 = -\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} R_1 - \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} R_1 + \\
 & + \sigma_0 (\sigma_3)'_{\eta_0} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^{k-1}}{k!(k-1)!} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n n!} \sigma_1^n F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) + \\
 & + \sigma_0 (\sigma_1)'_{\eta_0} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n (n-1)!} \sigma_1^n F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$+\sigma_0(\sigma_2)'_{n_0} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n} \sigma_1^n \frac{\beta(1-\beta)}{1+k+n} F(1+\beta, 2-\beta, 2+k+n; \sigma_2).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 = \\ & -\gamma(\eta - \eta_0) \sigma_0 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^{k-1}}{k!(k-1)!} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n} \sigma_1^n F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) + \\ & + \frac{(\eta - \eta_0)(\eta_0 + \xi)}{(\eta + \xi)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)^2} \sigma_0 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n \sigma_1^n}{(1+k)_n (n-1)!} F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) + \\ & + \frac{(\eta - \eta_0)(\xi - \eta_0)}{(\eta - \xi)(\eta_0 - \xi_0)^2} \sigma_0 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n \sigma_1^n}{(1+k)_n n!} \times \\ & \quad \times \frac{\beta(1-\beta)}{1+k+n} F(1+\beta, 2-\beta, 2+k+n; \sigma_2), \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 = \\ & -\gamma(\xi - \xi_0) \sigma_0 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^{k-1}}{k!(k-1)!} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n} \sigma_1^n F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) + \\ & + \frac{(\xi - \xi_0)(\eta + \xi_0)}{(\eta + \xi)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)^2} \sigma_0 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n \sigma_1^n}{(1+k)_n (n-1)!} F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) + \\ & + \frac{(\xi - \xi_0)(\xi_0 - \eta)}{(\eta - \xi)(\eta_0 - \xi_0)^2} \sigma_0 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n \sigma_1^n}{(1+k)_n n!} \times \\ & \quad \times \frac{\beta(1-\beta)}{1+k+n} F(1+\beta, 2-\beta, 2+k+n; \sigma_2). \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Putting $\eta = \eta_0$ in (17), we get

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} - \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 \right]_{\eta=\eta_0} = 0.$$

From (18), it easily follows that

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} - \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 \right]_{\xi=\xi_0-2\varepsilon} = 0.$$

Now consider the expression under the last integral in (15). Applying the formula [9]

$$F(a, b, c; x) = (1-x)^{c-a-b} F(c-a, c-b, c; x) \tag{19}$$

to the function $F(1+\beta, 2-\beta, 2+k+n; \sigma_2)$ in equality (18), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 = \\ & -\gamma(\xi - \xi_0) \sigma_0 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^{k-1}}{k!(k-1)!} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n} \sigma_1^n F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) + \\ & + \frac{(\xi - \xi_0)(\eta + \xi_0)}{(\eta + \xi)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)^2} \sigma_0 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n \sigma_1^n}{(1+k)_n (n-1)!} F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) + \\ & + \frac{(\xi - \xi_0)(\xi_0 - \eta)}{(\eta - \xi)(\eta_0 - \xi_0)^2} \sigma_0 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n \sigma_1^n}{(1+k)_n n!} \times \\ & \quad \times \frac{\beta(1-\beta)}{1+k+n} \left[\frac{(\eta - \xi_0)(\eta_0 - \xi)}{(\eta - \xi)(\eta_0 - \xi_0)} \right]^{k+n-1} F(1+k+n-\beta, k+n+\beta, 2+k+n; \sigma_2). \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

By formula [9]

$$H_2(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \varepsilon; x, y) = \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\gamma)_n (\delta)_n}{(1-\alpha)_n n!} y^n F(\alpha - n, \beta, \varepsilon; x),$$

from (6), we have

$$R_4(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0) = \chi \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta}}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^n}{k!(\beta)_k} \times \\ \times \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(\beta)_n n!} \sigma_1^n F\left(1 - \beta - k - n, 1 - \beta, 2 - 2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}\right). \tag{21}$$

And from the formula (21) it follows that

$$\frac{\partial R_4}{\partial \eta_0} = -\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} R_4 - \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \eta} R_4 + \\ + \chi \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta} (2\beta - 1)}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-2} (\sigma_2)'_{\eta_0} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\sigma_3)^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \times \\ \times \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{n!(\beta+k)_n} \sigma_1^n F\left(1 - \beta - k - n, 1 - \beta, 2 - 2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}\right) + \\ + [\gamma(\xi - \xi_0)] \chi \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta}}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-1} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(\sigma_3)^{k-1}}{(k-1)!(\beta)_k} \times \\ \times \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{n!(\beta+k)_n} \sigma_1^n F\left(1 - \beta - k - n, 1 - \beta, 2 - 2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}\right) + \\ + \chi(\sigma_1)'_{\eta_0} \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta}}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\sigma_3)^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \times \\ \times \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(n-1)!(\beta+k)_n} \sigma_1^{n-1} F\left(1 - \beta - k - n, 1 - \beta, 2 - 2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}\right) + \\ + \chi \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_2} \right)'_{\eta_0} \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta}}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\sigma_3)^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \times \\ \times \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{n!(\beta+k)_n} \sigma_1^n \frac{1 - \beta - k - n}{2} F\left(2 - \beta - k - n, 2 - \beta, 3 - 2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}\right).$$

Applying formula (19) to the function $F\left(2 - \beta - k - n, 2 - \beta, 3 - 2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}\right)$, from the latter equality, we

obtain

$$\frac{\partial R_4}{\partial \eta_0} + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_4 = \frac{\beta(\xi_0 - \eta)}{(\eta_0 - \eta)(\eta_0 - \xi_0)} R_4 + \\ + \frac{(\xi - \xi_0)(\xi_0 - \eta)}{(\eta - \xi)(\eta - \xi_0)^2} \chi \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta}}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\sigma_3)^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \times \\ \times \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{n!(\beta+k)_n} \sigma_1^n F\left(1 - \beta - k - n, 1 - \beta, 2 - 2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}\right) + \\ + [-\gamma(\xi - \xi_0)] \chi \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta}}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-1} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(\sigma_3)^{k-1}}{(k-1)!(\beta)_k} \times \\ \times \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{n!(\beta+k)_n} \sigma_1^n F\left(1 - \beta - k - n, 1 - \beta, 2 - 2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}\right) +$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{(\xi - \xi_0)(\eta + \xi_0)}{(\eta + \xi)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)^2} \chi \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta}}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\sigma_3)^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \times \\
& \times \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(n-1)!(\beta+k)_n} \sigma_1^{n-1} F \left(1-\beta-k-n, 1-\beta, 2-2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2} \right) + \\
& + \frac{(\eta - \xi)(\eta - \xi_0)}{(\xi - \xi_0)(\eta - \eta_0)^2} \chi \left(\frac{\eta + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{2\beta}}{[(\xi_0 - \xi)(\eta_0 - \eta)]^\beta} \sigma_2^{2\beta-1} \times \\
& \times \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\sigma_3)^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{n!(\beta+k)_n} \sigma_1^n \frac{1-\beta-k-n}{2} \times \\
& \times \left[\frac{(\eta - \xi_0)(\xi - \eta_0)}{(\xi - \xi_0)(\eta - \eta_0)} \right]^{k+n-1} F \left(1-\beta+k+n, 1-\beta, 3-2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2} \right). \quad (22)
\end{aligned}$$

Then from (20) and (22), substituting $\eta = \xi_0 + \varepsilon$ and $\eta = \xi_0 - \varepsilon$ respectively, and then passing to the limit at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ and taking into account the equality $F(a, b, c; 1) = \Gamma(c)\Gamma(c-a-b)/\Gamma(c-a)\Gamma(c-b)$ [9], we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 = \left(\frac{\xi_0 + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \left(\frac{\xi_0 - \xi}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right)^\beta [-\gamma(\xi - \xi_0)] \times \\
& \times \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^{k-1}}{k!(k-1)!} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{n!(1+k)_n} \sigma_1^n \frac{\Gamma(k+n)}{\Gamma(1-\beta+k+n)\Gamma(k+n+\beta)} + \\
& + \left(\frac{\xi_0 + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \left(\frac{\xi_0 - \xi}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right)^\beta \left[\frac{2\xi_0(\xi - \xi_0)}{(\xi_0 + \xi)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)^2} \right] \times \\
& \times \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(n-1)!(1+k)_n} \sigma_1^{n-1} \frac{\Gamma(k+n)}{\Gamma(1-\beta+k+n)\Gamma(k+n+\beta)} + \\
& + \frac{(\xi_0 - \xi)}{(\eta_0 - \xi_0)(\xi - \eta_0)} \left(\frac{\xi_0 + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \left(\frac{\xi_0 - \xi}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right)^\beta \frac{\beta(1-\beta)}{\Gamma(1+\beta)\Gamma(2-\beta)} + \\
& + \left(\frac{\xi_0 + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \left(\frac{\xi_0 - \xi}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right)^\beta \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{n!(1+k)_n} \sigma_1^n \frac{\beta(1-\beta)}{1+k+m} \times \\
& \times \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\varepsilon^{k+n} (\xi_0 + \varepsilon - \xi)}{(\eta_0 - \xi_0)(\xi - \eta_0)} \frac{\Gamma(2+k+n)\Gamma(1-k-n)}{\Gamma(1+\beta)\Gamma(2-\beta)}. \quad (23) \\
& \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_4 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_4 = \left(\frac{\xi_0 + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \left(\frac{\xi_0 - \xi}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right)^\beta [-\gamma(\xi - \xi_0)] \times \\
& \times \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^{k-1}}{(\beta)_k (k-1)!} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(\beta+k)_n n!} \sigma_1^n \frac{\chi \Gamma(k+n)\Gamma(\beta)\Gamma(2-2\beta)}{\Gamma(1-\beta+k+n)\Gamma(\beta+k+n)\Gamma(1-\beta)} + \\
& + \left(\frac{\xi_0 + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \left(\frac{\xi_0 - \xi}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right)^\beta \frac{2\xi_0(\xi - \xi_0)}{(\xi_0 + \xi)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)^2} \times \\
& \times \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(\beta)_k k!} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(\beta+k)_n (n-1)!} \sigma_1^{n-1} \frac{\chi \Gamma(k+n)\Gamma(\beta)\Gamma(2-2\beta)}{\Gamma(1-\beta+k+n)\Gamma(\beta+k+n)\Gamma(1-\beta)} + \\
& + \frac{\xi_0 - \xi}{(\eta_0 - \xi_0)(\xi - \eta_0)} \left(\frac{\xi_0 + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \left(\frac{\xi_0 - \xi}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right)^\beta \frac{\chi(1-\beta)\Gamma(3-2\beta)}{2\Gamma(2-\beta)\Gamma(2-\beta)} + \\
& + \left(\frac{\xi_0 + \xi}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} \right)^\alpha \left(\frac{\xi_0 - \xi}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right)^\beta \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{n!(\beta+k)_n} \sigma_1^n \times
\end{aligned}$$

$$\times \frac{1-\beta-k-n}{2} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\varepsilon^{k+n} (\xi_0 + \varepsilon - \xi)}{(\eta_0 - \xi_0)(\xi - \eta_0)} \frac{\chi \Gamma(3-2\beta) \Gamma(1-k-n)}{\Gamma(2-\beta-k-n) \Gamma(2-\beta-k-n)}. \tag{24}$$

From these equalities, by virtue of the value of c , it follows that

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_4 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_4 \right]_{\eta = \xi_0 - \varepsilon} - \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \eta_0} R_1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_0 + \xi_0} + \frac{\beta}{\eta_0 - \xi_0} \right) R_1 \right]_{\eta = \xi_0 + \varepsilon} \right\} = 0. \tag{25}$$

If we take into account equality (10), then due to equality (25), the limit at the $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ last integral in (15) is equal to zero.

Based on the above and the equality $R_1(\xi_0, \eta_0; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) = 1$, from (15) at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, it follows that $L[F(\xi_0, \eta_0)] = f(\xi_0, \eta_0)$, i.e. the function $F(\xi_0, \eta_0)$ satisfies equation (1).

Let us now prove that conditions (11) are satisfied. For this aim, we $F(\xi_0, \eta_0)$ rewrite the function in the form $F(\xi_0, \eta_0) = F_1(\xi_0, \eta_0) + F_4(\xi_0, \eta_0)$, where

$$F_1(\xi_0, \eta_0) = \int_0^{\xi_0} d\xi \int_{\xi_0}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) R_1(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta, \quad F_4(\xi_0, \eta_0) = \int_0^{\xi_0} d\xi \int_{\xi}^{\xi_0} f(\xi, \eta) R_4(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta.$$

Let's consider the function $F_1(\xi_0, \eta_0)$ the first. Taking into account equality (16), we rewrite the function $F_1(\xi_0, \eta_0)$ in the form

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(\xi_0, \eta_0) &= \int_0^{\xi_0} d\xi \int_{\xi_0}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) R_1(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0) d\eta = \\ &= (\eta_0 + \xi_0)^{-\alpha} (\eta_0 - \xi_0)^{-\beta} \int_0^{\xi_0} d\xi \int_{\xi_0}^{\eta_0} f(\xi, \eta) (\eta + \xi)^\alpha (\eta - \xi)^\beta \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{(k!)^2} \times \\ &\quad \times \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n n!} \sigma_1^n F(\beta, 1-\beta, 1+k+n; \sigma_2) d\eta. \end{aligned}$$

In the integral over ξ and η respectively perform the replacement $\xi = \xi_0 z, \eta = \eta_0 - (\eta_0 - \xi_0)t$:

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(\xi_0, \eta_0) &= (\eta_0 + \xi_0)^{-\alpha} (\eta_0 - \xi_0)^{1-\beta} \xi_0 \times \\ &\quad \times \int_0^1 (\eta_0 - \xi_0 z)^{\delta+\beta-1} (\eta_0 + \xi_0 z)^\alpha dz \int_0^1 A_1(z, t, \xi_0, \eta_0) dt, \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(z, t, \xi_0, \eta_0) &= \left[1 - \frac{\eta_0 - \xi_0}{\eta_0 + \xi_0 z} t \right]^\alpha \left[1 - \frac{\eta_0 - \xi_0}{\eta_0 - \xi_0 z} t \right]^{\beta+\delta-1} \times \\ &\quad \times f_1 \left[\xi_0 z, \eta_0 - (\eta_0 - \xi_0)t \right] \times \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{[\gamma(\xi_0 z - \xi_0)(\eta_0 - \xi_0)t]^k}{(k!)^2} \times \\ &\quad \times \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(1+k)_n n!} \left[\frac{(\xi_0 z - \xi_0)(\eta_0 - \xi_0)t}{(\eta_0 + \xi_0 z - (\eta_0 - \xi_0)t)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)} \right]^n \times \\ &\quad \times F \left(\beta, \beta + k + n, 1 + k + n; -\frac{(\xi_0 z - \xi_0)t}{\eta_0 - \xi_0 z - (\eta_0 - \xi_0)t} \right). \end{aligned}$$

This implies the validity of the following equalities:

$$\lim_{\eta_0 \rightarrow \xi_0} A_1(z, t, \xi_0, \eta_0) = f_1(\xi_0 z, \eta_0) F(\beta, \beta, 1; t), \tag{27}$$

$$A_1(z, t, 0, \eta_0) = (1-t)^{\alpha+\beta+\delta-1} f_1(0, \eta_0 - \eta_0 t). \tag{28}$$

Then, due to the uniform convergence of the series, it follows from equalities (26), (27), (28) that the conditions

$$\lim_{\eta_0 \rightarrow \xi_0} F_1(\xi_0, \eta_0) = 0, \quad F_1(\xi_0, \eta_0) \Big|_{\xi_0=0} = 0. \quad (29)$$

Let's now consider the function $F_4(\xi_0, \eta_0)$. Taking into account equality (21), we rewrite the function $F_4(\xi_0, \eta_0)$ in the form

$$F_4(\xi_0, \eta_0) = \int_0^{\xi_0} d\xi \int_{\xi}^{\xi_0} f(\xi, \eta) R_4(\xi, \eta; \xi_0, \eta_0; \gamma) d\eta = \chi(\eta_0 + \xi_0)^{-\alpha} (\eta_0 - \xi_0)^{1-2\beta} \times \\ \times \int_0^{\xi_0} (\xi_0 - \xi)^{\beta-1} d\xi \int_{\xi}^{\xi_0} (\eta - \xi)(\eta + \xi)^{\alpha} (\eta - \eta_0)^{\beta-1} f(\xi, \eta) \times \\ \times \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_3^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(\beta+k)_n n!} (-\sigma_1)^n F\left(1-\beta-k-n, 1-\beta, 2-2\beta; \frac{1}{\sigma_2}\right) d\eta.$$

In integrals with respect to ξ and η replacing by $\xi = \xi_0 z$, $\eta = \xi_0 - (\xi_0 - \xi)t$, we have

$$F_4(\xi_0, \eta_0) = \chi(\eta_0 + \xi_0)^{-\alpha} (\eta_0 - \xi_0)^{1-2\beta} \xi_0^{\beta+\delta+1} \eta_0^{\beta-1} \times \\ \times \int_0^1 (1-z)^{\beta+\varepsilon} \left(1 - \frac{\xi_0}{\eta_0} z\right)^{\beta-1} dz \int_0^1 A_4(z, t, \xi_0, \eta_0) dt, \quad (30)$$

where

$$A_4(z, t, \xi_0, \eta_0) = [2z + (1-z)t]^{\alpha} t^{\delta} \left(1 - \frac{\xi_0 - \xi_0 z}{\eta_0 - \xi_0 z} t\right)^{\beta-1} f_1[\xi_0 z, \xi_0 - (\xi_0 - \xi) t] \times \\ \times \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{[\gamma(\xi_0 z - \xi_0)(\eta_0 - \xi_0 - (\xi_0 z - \xi_0)t)]^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \times \\ \times \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(\beta+k)_n n!} \left[\frac{(\xi_0 z - \xi_0)(\eta_0 - \xi_0 - (\xi_0 z - \xi_0)t)}{(\xi_0 + \xi_0 z - (\xi_0 - \xi_0 z)t)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)} \right]^n \times \\ \times F\left(1-\beta-k-n, 1-\beta, 2-2\beta; -\frac{(1-t)(\eta_0 - \xi_0)}{(\eta_0 - \xi_0 + (\xi_0 - \xi_0 z)t)}\right).$$

This implies the validity of the following equalities:

$$\lim_{\eta_0 \rightarrow \xi_0} A_4(z, t, \xi_0, \eta_0) = [2z + (1-z)t]^{\alpha} t^{\delta} (1-t)^{\beta-1} f_1(\xi_0 z, \xi_0 - (\xi_0 - \xi_0 z)t) \times \\ \times \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{[-\gamma(\xi_0 z - \xi_0)^2 t]^k}{k!(\beta)_k} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n (\alpha)_n (1-\alpha)_n}{(\beta+k)_n n!} \left[\frac{-(\xi_0 z - \xi_0)^2 t}{\xi_0(1+z - (1-z)t)(\eta_0 + \xi_0)} \right]^n, \quad (31)$$

$$A_4(z, t, 0, \eta_0) = [2z + (1-z)t]^{\alpha} t^{\delta} f_1(0, 0) F(1-\beta, 1-\beta, 2-2\beta; 1-t). \quad (32)$$

Then, due to the uniform convergence of the series, it follows from equalities (30), (31), (32) that the conditions

$$\lim_{\eta_0 \rightarrow \xi_0} F_4(\xi_0, \eta_0) = 0, \quad F_4(\xi_0, \eta_0) \Big|_{\xi_0=0} = 0. \quad (33)$$

By virtue of $F(\xi_0, \eta_0) = F_1(\xi_0, \eta_0) + F_4(\xi_0, \eta_0)$, the equalities (29) and (33) imply that conditions (11) are satisfied.

Theorem has been completed.

References:

1. Saigo M. A Certain boundary value problem for the Euler-Darboux equations // Math. Japonica, 1977. -No. 24. -p. 377-385.
2. Saigo M. On a property of the Appell hypergeometric function F_1 // Math. Rep. College GeneralEd. Kyushu Univ., 1980. -No. 12. -p. 63-67.
3. Saigo M. A Certain boundary value problem for the Euler-Darboux equations II // Math. Japonica, 1980. -No. 25. -p. 211-220.
4. Saigo M. A Certain boundary value problem for the Euler-Darboux equations III // Math. Japonica, 1981. -No. 26. -p. 103-119.
5. Khasanov A. Hypergeometric functions and their applications to solving boundary value problems for degenerate second order differential equations. Diss. Doctor of Physics and Mathematics Sciences. - Tashkent. 2009. -240p.
6. Urinov AK, Karimov Sh.T. Erdelyi-Kober operators and their applications to partial differential

equations. -Fergana. Publishing house Fergana., 2021. 200 p.

7. Urinov A.K., Ismoilov A.I., Mamanazarov.AO Darboux problem for the generalized Euler-Poisson-Darboux equation // Ukrainian Mathematical Journal, 2017. -69, no.1. -p . – 52-70.

8. Urinov A.K., Ismoilov A.I. On the solvability of the Cauchy-Goursat problem for the generalized Euler-Poisson-Darboux equation // Bulletin of the Institute of Mathematics 2018. No. 1.-p.9-22.

9. Bateman G., Erdelyi A. Higher transcendental functions. hypergeometric function. legendre functions. -M.: Nauka, 1965. -296 p.